

PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING THE CORPORATE CULTURE OF PEDAGOGUES OF A NON-STATE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION, PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS – CONDITIONS

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Annotation: this article explores the principles and pedagogical conditions essential for improving the corporate culture of teachers in non-state preschool educational organizations. It emphasizes the significance of fostering a positive, collaborative work environment that enhances both teacher well-being and pedagogical effectiveness.

Key principles for cultivating a strong corporate culture include promoting open communication, teamwork, leadership support, recognition, and work-life balance. Concurrently, improving pedagogical conditions through continuous professional development, access to adequate teaching resources, classroom autonomy, and mentorship is critical for empowering educators.

The article underscores the interdependence of corporate culture and pedagogical conditions, suggesting that a harmonious integration of both leads to greater teacher satisfaction, retention, and overall educational quality. By focusing on these principles and conditions, non-state preschools can create an environment that supports both the professional growth of educators and the optimal development of their students.

Key words: teamwork, leadership support, recognition, satisfaction, retention, pedagogical.

In the realm of early childhood education, the quality of both corporate culture and pedagogical conditions plays a pivotal role in determining the success of a non-governmental preschool educational organization. Establishing a positive, supportive corporate culture alongside optimal pedagogical conditions can significantly enhance the professional development of educators, improve student outcomes, and foster a harmonious working environment. This article delves into the principles that contribute to improving both aspects within non-governmental preschool institutions, ensuring that they are conducive to effective teaching and learning.

1. Principles of improving corporate culture in preschool education.

Corporate culture in any organization, including non-governmental preschools, refers to the shared values, norms, practices, and behaviors that shape the working environment. A positive corporate culture influences not only employee satisfaction

but also enhances overall educational outcomes. To improve corporate culture in a preschool setting, consider the following principles:

a. Fostering open communication channels are essential to creating a culture of trust and collaboration. Regular meetings, feedback sessions, and transparent discussions between leadership and teaching staff can foster a sense of inclusion. Teachers should feel comfortable sharing ideas, voicing concerns, and contributing to decision-making processes. Encouraging an open-door policy and peer-to-peer dialogue further enhances communication within the team.

b. Collaboration and teamwork promoting a collaborative environment encourages teamwork among educators. Regular opportunities for teachers to work together on projects, plan joint lessons, and share best practices strengthen professional relationships and increase the collective effectiveness of the teaching staff. It's important to create a supportive environment where collaboration is valued more than competition.

c. Recognition and appreciation recognizing and appreciating teachers' efforts is crucial for sustaining motivation and morale. Simple acts of recognition, whether in the form of verbal praise, awards, or professional development opportunities, can make educators feel valued and understood. Such recognition boosts job satisfaction and reinforces a positive corporate culture.

d. Leadership support and vision effective leadership is foundational to cultivating a strong corporate culture. Leaders within non-governmental preschools should clearly articulate the organization's vision, mission, and values, ensuring they align with the aspirations of the educators. Supportive leadership empowers teachers to pursue excellence in their teaching and professional growth, reinforcing a culture of continuous improvement.

e. Work-life balance and teacher well-being promoting work-life balance and addressing teachers' well-being are essential for maintaining a healthy corporate culture. Overworked and stressed educators can experience burnout, which negatively affects their effectiveness and overall morale. Providing reasonable workloads, regular breaks, and access to mental health support creates a more balanced, sustainable work environment.

2. Principles of improving pedagogical conditions for teachers pedagogical conditions refer to the environment, resources, and support systems available to educators for carrying out their teaching responsibilities. Improving these conditions is key to enhancing the quality of education and ensuring teachers can perform at their best. The following principles focus on creating favorable pedagogical conditions:

a. Access to professional development continual professional development is critical for teachers to stay updated with the latest educational trends, methodologies,

and best practices. Non-governmental preschool organizations should offer regular training, workshops, and seminars that enhance teachers' pedagogical skills. Encouraging teachers to attend external conferences or obtain certifications further promotes a culture of lifelong learning.

b. Adequate teaching resources teachers require access to appropriate teaching materials and resources to create engaging, effective lessons. Non-governmental preschools should ensure that classrooms are equipped with age-appropriate educational tools, books, toys, and technology that facilitate interactive learning experiences. An investment in resources positively impacts both teacher performance and student engagement.

c. Classroom autonomy teachers should have the freedom to design and implement their own curriculum, within the broader framework set by the organization. Allowing teachers to adapt teaching methods to suit the unique needs of their students fosters creativity and innovation in lesson delivery. Autonomy in the classroom promotes teacher ownership of the learning process and helps them feel more invested in their work.

d. Mentorship and peer support mentorship programs are invaluable for novice teachers or those seeking professional growth. Senior or experienced educators can offer guidance, share insights, and provide emotional and professional support. In addition to mentorship, peer collaboration and regular feedback exchanges contribute to a culture of continuous improvement.

e. Well-defined expectations and support structures clear, well-structured expectations for teaching, assessment, and administrative duties are essential for teachers to thrive. Teachers should be equipped with the tools and knowledge to meet these expectations effectively. Additionally, robust support structures such as teaching assistants, administrative staff, and clear reporting lines ensure that educators are not overwhelmed and can focus on what they do best—teaching.

f. Creating a positive learning environment the learning environment itself must be safe, inclusive, and stimulating. Preschool classrooms should be designed with the child's developmental needs in mind, fostering creativity, curiosity, and engagement. The physical and psychological environment plays a significant role in both teachers' and students' performance. When teachers are able to work in a well-organized, positive environment, they are more likely to deliver high-quality teaching.

3. Integrating corporate culture and pedagogical conditions while corporate culture and pedagogical conditions can be viewed as separate concepts, they are closely interconnected. A strong corporate culture supports the development of positive pedagogical conditions, while excellent pedagogical conditions enhance the overall organizational climate. To integrate both:

- Encourage teacher-led initiatives: Give teachers the autonomy to create educational programs or corporate culture activities that reflect both their pedagogical interests and the organization's values. This integration can enhance engagement and ownership.

- Evaluate and improve together: Both corporate culture and pedagogical conditions should be regularly assessed through surveys, feedback, and observation. When these aspects are continually evaluated and improved together, organizations can ensure a consistent, high-quality experience for both teachers and students.

Conclusion.

Improving the corporate culture and pedagogical conditions of teachers in non-governmental preschool educational organizations is essential to foster a positive and productive work environment. By focusing on open communication, collaboration, professional development, and teacher well-being, these institutions can support their educators in delivering high-quality education. Simultaneously, investing in appropriate teaching resources, creating conducive learning environments, and empowering teachers with autonomy ensures that they can thrive pedagogically. Ultimately, the integration of strong corporate culture and pedagogical support creates a foundation for sustainable growth and excellence in early childhood education.

List of used literature:

1. Yuldoshev J., Hasanov S. Pedagogical technologies. – T.: Finance-Economy, 2009.

2. Mahkamova M. Yu. Formation of a culture of pedagogical communication of future educators: Ped.fan.nomz.... diss. author ref. – T.: 1999. – 22 p.

3. Muslimov N.A., Usmonboyeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., Turayev A.B. Fundamentals of pedagogical competence and creativity – Tashkent, 2015.

4. Mutalipova M.J., Khodjaev B.Kh. Comparative pedagogy. -T: 2015

5. Mukhina S.A., Solovyova A.A. Modern innovative technology of education. – M. Geotar-Media, 2008. – 43 p.

6. Ru'ziyeva D., Usmonboyeva M., Holikova Z. Interactive methods: essence and application G' Met.k'll. – T.: Nizamiy named DTPU, 2013. – 115 p.